

Exploration of Current Health Information for Recently Released Individuals from jail and prisons for the Development of a Health Website

Hind Akasbi, DVM, MS Population Health Informatics
CUNY School of Public Health

Abstract

Background

The high mortality rate among recently released individuals from incarceration is a pressing concern. This population faces an elevated risk of death, especially within the first two weeks post-release, emphasizing the need for an effective reentry support. The objective of this study is to comprehensively investigate the health-related challenges confronted by individuals released from incarceration. This includes a thorough analysis of current health data and an examination of the existing online information landscape tailored to recently released individuals.

Approach

We adopt a comprehensive approach that combines a thorough literature review and content analysis to address the health challenges faced by recently released individuals during their transition to the community. The literature review serves as a foundational element, providing valuable insights into the multifaceted nature of health challenges within this population. Building on the insights gained from the literature review, our study incorporates a content analysis focused on evaluating the sufficiency and relevance of available websites tailored to recently released individuals in New York State (NYS). By integrating findings from both the literature review and content analysis, we aim to develop a comprehensive understanding of the current landscape of health information and services available to recently released individuals, thereby informing strategies for improvement and enhancement in this critical area.

Conclusions

The study highlights the multifaceted nature of health issues faced by formerly incarcerated individuals, encompassing substance abuse, cardiovascular diseases, uncontrolled hypertension, mental health disorders, and an elevated risk of HIV diagnosis. These complexities underscore the urgency of addressing the diverse health needs of this population. Moreover, the fragmentation of resources and gaps in health education underscore the necessity for a comprehensive and centralized platform.

Introduction

Individuals recently released from incarceration face a disproportionately high risk of mortality. Within the initial two weeks after release, the risk of death is 12.7 times higher than that of the general population.¹ The shift from incarceration to reintegrating into the community presents several obstacles, such as restricted availability of essential healthcare resources and information.² People who have recently been released from incarceration often struggle with navigating the complex healthcare system, which can result in insufficient use of healthcare services and worsen existing health issues.³

Providing effective reentry assistance and ensuring well-informed health choices are crucial steps towards minimizing health disparities among this population. Considering that the risk of mortality is highest in the early days and weeks after release, timely access to healthcare, health information, and ongoing health management is important to enhance the successful reintegration and empower recently released individuals. Poor health outcomes for recently released individuals are more likely due to the limited availability of easily comprehensible health information.⁴ Improving the general health and prospects of those who have recently been released from incarceration requires the creation of a user-centric, educational, and easily accessible health program.⁵

In this study, we conducted a literature review in order to gain insights about the health challenges recently released individuals encounter during their transition to the community. The insights gained from this literature review will play an important role in shaping our approach to evaluating websites that provide resources for released individuals. This exploratory study also included a content analysis of available websites for released individuals in NYS. We will be exploring the content of the websites that serve released individuals to provide a comprehensive understanding on the health information available online for this population.

Content analysis is a research methodology that originated in the 1950s with the study of mass media. It is a systematic, rigorous approach to analyzing diverse communication forms, including websites obtained or generated during research.⁶ In today's digital era, characterized by abundant information, content analysis persists as an essential instrument for researchers seeking to navigate the complexities of online communication.

Therefore, the objectives of this study were to examine the health-related challenges faced by individuals released from incarceration and evaluate the current health data and online information available for this population. Findings will be used for ongoing development of a conceptual plan for a health website with the goal of equipping individuals with the information and resources necessary to make well-informed health choices and facilitate their successful reintegration into society.

Literature review:

The approach to the research was that of scoping review.⁷ The scoping review aimed to systematically investigate the existing body of literature concerning the health needs of recently released individuals, as well as the primary factors contributing to poor health and mortality rates within this population. Additionally, the review sought to identify any notable gaps in accessing

health information for recently released individuals. The study addressed three primary research questions:

- What are the primary factors contributing to poor health and mortality rates among recently released individuals?
- What online information is available regarding the health needs of recently released individuals?
- Are there any gaps on accessing health information and resources for recently released individuals?

Search strategies:

We established a comprehensive search strategy to find relevant literature, by conducting searches on PubMed and Google Scholar. The search terms were strategically chosen to encapsulate key concepts: (1) released individuals and mortality, (2) former incarcerated and poor health, (3) released individuals and poor health, (4) former incarcerated and mortality.

The criteria for inclusion were designed to directly address the research questions, covering the needs and health challenges experienced by formerly incarcerated or recently released individuals. Additionally, studies exploring mortality within this population were also considered for inclusion. This encompassed primary research and reviews published in English between 2000 and 2023. By including articles from 2000 to 2023, we emphasize the focus on relevant literature. This timeframe ensures that our literature review comprises the most current and relevant studies, offering a comprehensive understanding of the health needs and challenges faced by recently released individuals. This approach guarantees that the gathered information accurately reflects the present situation.

Exclusion criteria involve articles that do not specifically explore or provide insights into the health and mortality of released individuals, studies that are irrelevant to the research questions, such as those focusing on unrelated health topics like recidivism, as well as studies about COVID-19 in inmates and those with unavailable full texts.

Study Identification

374 articles were identified, after exclusion of duplicates, The initial round of title and abstract screening of 234 articles generated a pool of 79 potentially relevant articles. Subsequently, a comprehensive full-text review further refined the selection, which ultimately resulted in the inclusion of 23 articles for comprehensive analysis. (Figure1)

The size of our selected articles seems small for a literature review, but this number is appropriate to this study that revolves around content analysis. Unlike broader reviews, we've intentionally kept our scope narrow and focused.

Figure 1

Findings

Factors contributing to poor health and mortality rates among recently released individuals

Numerous studies have demonstrated a concerning tendency toward elevated mortality rates among individuals with a history of incarceration.⁸ Released individuals have higher mortality rates, chronic health problems, mental health issues, infectious diseases, suicidal thoughts, and cardiovascular conditions.⁹ Upon reentry into society, many former inmates struggle with drug and alcohol addiction as well as physical and mental problems.¹⁰ Recently released individuals face a significantly higher risk of suicide compared to the general population, particularly in the initial weeks following their release.^{11,12} The likelihood of suicide in this population is approaching levels observed in discharged psychiatric patients.¹¹ This heightened risk is believed to be associated with the elevated prevalence of mental health issues observed in prisoners, combined with the challenges of transitioning from a prison environment to community life.¹³

After opioid overdose, cardiovascular diseases were shown to be the second highest cause of mortality in a research including 76,208 people released from the Washington State Department of Corrections.¹⁴ Studies also show that people who have recently been incarcerated are more likely to have uncontrolled blood pressure,¹⁵ and have a greater incidence of cancer.¹⁶ Additionally, studying the relationship between prison release and HIV infection rates reveals a clear connection between release from incarceration and the high rate of HIV diagnoses.¹⁷

Research on the utilization of Emergency departments among recently discharged prisoners reveals that within the first year after release, visits to the Emergency department by ex-prisoners were notably more associated with mental health issues and substance use problems.¹⁸

The acute risk of opioid overdose following release is also recognized by numerous research on post-incarceration mortality.^{14,19,20,21,22,23,24,25} According to O'Connor et al., psychostimulants and heroin are the major causes of substance-related death for newly released prisoners.¹⁹ Drug-related deaths among individuals formerly incarcerated are more likely to occur in the first two weeks following release. During this time released individuals are eight times more likely to die from drug-related causes.²⁰ A study conducted in Washington state revealed that the risk of death among

former prisoners in the first two weeks post-release was 12.7 times higher compared to other state residents. Specifically, the risk of death from drug overdose in this period was 129 times higher.²⁶ This further highlights the critical nature of the initial weeks following release, warranting targeted preventive programs to mitigate these risks.

Many studies have shown incarceration history as a risk factor for overdose deaths.¹⁴ According to recent data, unintentional poisoning, of which overdose is a subcategory, is the leading cause of death after release from prison.²¹ The transition from incarceration to community reintegration presents a critical window of vulnerability for individuals at risk of fatal unintentional drug overdoses.²⁰ Therefore, research consistently demonstrates that the likelihood of former incarcerated dying in the first two weeks after releasing due to drug-related causes is an urgent concern.

On the other hand, mental health conditions, are prevalent among formerly incarcerated individuals, contributing to a complex challenge.²⁷ This condition not only poses a direct risk to health, but it also has been linked to a reduced ability to get medical treatment and may aggravate chronic medical conditions, such as diabetes and cardiovascular disease.²⁶ Studies have demonstrated that unresolved mental health issues increase the likelihood of rearrest and drug use, particularly in women.²⁸

The possible effects for physical health could become more serious when mental health demands are unmet for a longer period. Stressors like reentry have a negative impact on one's physical health because they can worsen illnesses like anxiety and depression. Furthermore, it is estimated that up to 41% of people who are incarcerated suffer from both addiction and mental illness concurrently.⁹

Reviewing the research articles reveals that mental health issues and opioid overdoses emerge as predominant factors contributing to post-release mortality. The relationship between mental health challenges, opioid abuse, and post-incarceration mortality shed the light on the underlying dynamics and recommend targeted interventions for this vulnerable population.

Health needs of recently released individuals.

In addition to the highlighted health concerns, it is imperative to address the broader spectrum of health needs for recently released individuals. Beyond drug overdose prevention, there is a pressing need for comprehensive healthcare support tailored to their unique circumstances. This includes proactive education on various health risks and the implementation of specialized measures to safeguard their well-being.^{25,29} Transitional programs targeted at mitigating risky substance use and addressing mental health issues have emerged as crucial interventions for released individuals. These programs should ideally commence prior to release and continue post-release to maximize their effectiveness.²⁴ Moreover, ongoing surveillance of mortality trends among individuals with a history of incarceration is essential. This underscores the imperative of sustained efforts to prevent and treat various health problems, particularly substance use disorders. Timely identification of substance use, whether prior to or during incarceration, can significantly improve access to necessary treatment and subsequently lead to enhanced health outcomes.¹⁹

Ensuring comprehensive healthcare services for incarcerated individuals struggling with substance abuse is of paramount importance. This support should extend throughout their time within the criminal justice system and seamlessly transition into the post-release phase to facilitate their

successful reintegration into society. The integration of pre-release drug services with appropriate aftercare is crucial in maintaining uninterrupted service delivery and ensuring that individuals struggling with substance dependence receive consistent and uninterrupted care.²⁰ By addressing these multifaceted health needs, we can work towards a more holistic and effective approach to the healthcare of recently released individuals.

Gaps in accessing health information for recently released individuals.

Existing studies underscore significant barriers to accessing physical and mental health care post-release. According to a qualitative assessment of the health experiences of newly released inmates, these barriers include a lack of awareness regarding available services, protracted wait times, and challenges in obtaining chronic medication refills. Such delays in healthcare accessibility present a considerable obstacle to individuals striving to maintain their health during the reentry period.³⁰ Furthermore, the brief duration of chronic medication supplies provided to former inmates upon release, typically ranging from 10 to 30 days, raises concerns about the continuity of care.³⁰ As a result, individuals find it difficult to establish a consistent healthcare routine in their communities, especially when it comes to medication management, which highlights a clear gap in ensuring uninterrupted healthcare services for this population.

Additionally, released individuals state that it is challenging to maintain a medical care continuity between incarceration and post-release care. The barriers to obtaining essential healthcare services are made more difficult by this discontinuity and difficulties with appointment scheduling.³⁰ This denotes a structural gap in the coordination of the provision of healthcare during this crucial transitional period. On the other hand, the prevalence of mental health problems and substance use issues among inmates further complicates their reentry process. These conditions contribute to additional obstacles in meeting their physical health needs.⁹ While transitional care programs hold promise in providing pre- and post-release treatment and support, the research in this area has not yet yielded conclusive results.²² Therefore, further investigation and evaluation of such interventions are imperative to bridge the existing gap in healthcare support for recently released individuals. Studies have demonstrated that addressing these significant comorbid treatment challenges, especially during reintegration, may be possible through the provision of social support and a supportive network upon release. Establishing and maintaining connections with a strong support network could potentially play a pivotal role in mitigating adverse physical and mental health outcomes following release from incarceration.⁹ This highlights the importance of addressing the social dimensions of reentry to bridge the gap in health information and support for this vulnerable population.

Content Analysis:

To evaluate the quality and accessibility of health-related information, a comprehensive content analysis of websites serving recently released individuals in New York State will be conducted.

This content analysis serves as an exploratory investigation into the alignment between web content and the specific information needs of recently released individuals. Specifically, we aim to assess the sufficiency and reliability of information on prevalent medical issues, including overdose, HIV, and mental health, provided by the evaluated websites. Additionally, our exploration extends to examining the adequacy of outlining health services and treatment alternatives within the content.

Methods:

This content analysis aims to identify the sufficiency of the websites by identifying what information is being shared currently in relation to health. Additionally, the quality of the material included on the websites was also assessed using DISCERN tool. Furthermore, an evaluation was conducted to determine the extent to which the content aligns with the specific needs of the target population.

The assessment of website sufficiency centered on the inclusion of health information tailored to former incarcerated individuals. The presence or absence of content about the factors contributing to poor health and mortality among recently released individuals identified in the literature review, was systematically examined. Websites were deemed deficient if they lacked information concerning mental health issues, substance use, HIV/AIDS, and chronic health issues.

The DISCERN tool instrument is used to assess the websites' information quality. The tool includes 16 questions that are used to assess whether the material is accurate, up to date, and unbiased. For the purpose of this study, I will utilize the six categories that were previously mentioned by Rao et al., as grouping the 16 components of the DISCERN instrument.³¹ Each category question was rated on a scale of 1 to 5. A rating of 5 meant the website provided helpful and relevant information, while a rating of 1 indicated a lack of information in the mentioned categories.³¹

The selected websites were also assessed in accordance with the two health needs identified for recently released individuals in the literature review. These needs involve the provision of comprehensive healthcare services and transitional programs aimed at addressing risky substance use and mental health issues.

Websites that support and educate recently released individuals in New York State were found using a Google search. Google was picked as the search engine because it is the most widely used search engine to get health information, with more than 70% of online searches.³² To ensure rigor and broad search various terms were employed for the web search, including: (1) former incarcerated individuals and health education in NY, (2) Resources for recently released individuals in NYS, (3) former incarcerated and health services in NYS. Each search term has generated a large number of results (Table 1). Recognizing that individuals conducting online searches generally do not extend their examination beyond the initial two pages of results³³, priority was given to reviewing the first 20 retrieved websites.

Table 1

Search term	Number of search results	Duplicated from the first 20
Former incarcerated individuals and health education in NYS	27,100,000	0 (n=20)
Resources for recently released individuals in NYS	476,000,000	1 (n=19)
former incarcerated and health services in NYS	493,000,000	3 (n=17)

To be included in this review, websites had to satisfy two specific criteria: (1) offering explicit support for individuals with a history of incarceration, and (2) providing resources targeted to NYS released individuals. Exclusion criteria included sites that are designed for health professionals, advocates, academic research papers and news journals. The PRISMA flow diagram was employed to systematically outline the search findings.

Results:

Using the search terms a total of 57 websites were identified, after exclusion of duplicates (14), and ineligible sites (30), a total of 12 websites were subjected to evaluation, with 5 ultimately selected for the final analysis (Figure 2).

Website 1: Fortune society³⁴ is a nonprofit organization based in New York City that focuses on supporting and advocating for individuals who have been incarcerated or involved in the criminal justice system.

Website 2: Legal action center³⁵ is a nonprofit organization based in the United States that focuses on advocacy and legal support related to issues such as criminal justice, substance use disorders, HIV/AIDS, and discrimination.

Website 3: Re-entry programs³⁶ is an initiative designed to support individuals returning to the community after incarceration, it lists resources to help those looking for help. State Help, Federal Government Help, Non-Profit Organizations, etc.

Website 4: Probation information network³⁷ is a platform that provide information and access to reentry resources.

Website 5: NYC 311³⁸ is a non-emergency phone number and online platform that provide services and support to recently released incarcerated people in multiple areas including mental health, behavioral health, and physical health care.

Figure 2

1. Sufficiency of the websites:

The five eligible websites were assessed based on their provision of health information and/or resources related to the factors described in the literature review, which contribute to poor health and high mortality rates among released individuals (Table 2).

Regarding mental health issues and substance use that were considered as predominant contributors to post-release mortality in the literature review, 80% of the sites (n=4) incorporated information or services related to mental health. However, website 3, did not feature any resources on mental health. For substance use, 60% (n=3) of the websites provided information and resources, while websites 3 and 5, lacked information on substance use. Regarding HIV and chronic health issues, 60% of the websites did not include any health information or resources on these topics, with only two, website 1 and 5, mentioning services and information related to HIV/AIDS and chronic health issues.

Table 2

Health information/Resources about	Total present
Mental health issues	80% (4)
Substance use	60% (3)
HIV/AIDS	40% (2)
Blood pressure/ chronic health issues	40% (2)

2. Quality of sites using DISCERN tool

To assess the quality of information on the websites two raters employed the DISCERN tool to assess the quality of information. (Table 3). The final assessment for the website was derived by taking the average of all the combined scores (Figure 3).

In assessing the objectives of the five websites, they all received high scores ranging from 4 to 5, indicating excellence in clearly stating their primary objective, except website 5 that lacks clarity in stating its objective. In terms of relevance, Website 1 stands out with a high score of 4.5 on the DISCERN tool. This website provides a different articles, videos, and resources tailored to empower recently released individuals. Websites 2 and 5 also make positive contributions, receiving a score of 3.5. Website 2 provide resources and reports on addiction and mental health resources, while Website 5, although offering health care services, lacks educational materials. In contrast, websites 3 and 4 fall behind due to their restricted relevance, predominantly functioning as platforms that gather re-entry programs without providing tailored health services or educational information for this population.

Regarding information credibility, Websites 1 and 2 provide references for their included materials, whether articles or blog posts. Conversely, the other three websites struggle in this aspect, lacking both references and substantial educational health content. Notably, despite this shortfall, the websites maintain credibility in presenting accurate information about the services they offer, such as addresses and contact details.

In terms of treatment choices, all websites, except for Website 2, exhibit a commitment to providing treatment options for recently released individuals, including information on clinics, treatment centers, and counseling services. Website 2, focusing on educational resources, receives a lower score of 1.5 in this category. Similarly, concerning treatment effects, only Website 1 provides detailed information about each service, including therapy practices and enrollment plans, setting it apart from the other four websites, which lack clarity on their treatment options.

In the prevention category, Website 1 offers a health care coordination service to help manage and prevent health issues for the target population. Website 5 also contributes positively providing services specifically designed for those at risk for HIV/AIDS. However, Websites 3, 4, and 5 fall short in this category, lacking resources that effectively address the management and prevention of health issues.

Overall, website 1, emerges as the highest quality, earning a DISCERN score of 4.5. In contrast, Website 5, a government website, scores 3.1. Notably, Websites 2, 3, and 4 lag behind, all receiving DISCERN ratings below 3, indicating room for improvement in the overall quality and relevance of their content. (Figure 3)

Table 3

Categories	Question	Example	Score (1-5)									
			Website 1		Website 2		Website 3		Website 4		Website 5	
			Rater 1	Rater 2	Rater 1	Rater 2	Rater 1	Rater 2	Rater 1	Rater 2	Rater 1	Rater 2
Objective	Is the website's primary objective clear?	The website's homepage prominently states the main purpose or mission	5	4	5	5	4	5	5	5	3	2
Relevance	Does the website effectively address the prevalent health challenges faced by recently released individuals, providing clear and pertinent information?	The website offers articles, videos and resources specifically tailored to address the health concerns prevalent among recently released individuals, like sections on addiction recovery, mental health support or any educational materials.	5	4	3	4	2	2	2	2	3	4
Information credibility	Are there credible references or sources cited to support the information provided on the website, demonstrating a commitment to accuracy and reliability?	The website includes references from recognized medical journals or peer-reviewed articles, government health agencies to support the information provided	4	4	4	4	2	2	2	3	3	3
Treatment choices	Does the website furnish specific services or resources designed to assist recently released individuals in effectively	The website includes information on clinics, treatment centers, counseling services.	4	5	1	2	4	4	4	3	5	5

	managing their health conditions?											
Treatment effect	Does the website offer clear, balanced information on treatment options, covering how they work, benefits, risks, and their impact on quality of life?	If the website offers a treatment or service, does it outline different methods and provide specifics, such as emphasizing the importance of regular attendance for maximizing the benefits of the service?	5	4	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1
Prevention	Does the website provide additional resources that emphasize techniques for managing and preventing health issues?	The website provides informative articles, videos or any resources that cover topics like maintaining mental well-being after release, reducing the risk of overdose, managing blood pressure...	4	3	3	3	1	2	1	2	4	3
			4.5	4	2.8	3.1	2.3	2.6	2.5	2.8	3.1	3

Figure 3

3. Health needs in the websites:

To evaluate the incorporation of essential health needs outlined in the literature review, we examined websites based on two key health requirements: the provision of comprehensive healthcare services and the inclusion of transitional programs addressing substance use and/or mental health issues. These needs were categorized as either present or absent on the websites. Notably, an equal proportion of 60% indicated the presence of these needs on the websites, while 40% lacked in their provision. Websites 1, 4, and 5 demonstrated a commitment to providing comprehensive healthcare services, whereas Websites 2 and 3 lacked such healthcare offerings. Regarding transitional programs, Websites 1, 3, and 5 presented information on programs tailored for released individuals dealing with substance use and/or mental health issues, while Websites 2 and 4 did not offer any information on transitional programs (Table 4).

Table 4

Health needs	Total present
Comprehensive healthcare services	60% (3)
Transitional programs that address substance use and/or mental health issues.	60% (3)

Discussion:

This content analysis highlights the abundance of information and services available in New York State (NYS) to empower recently released individuals and enhance their general health outcomes. However, it's clear that these resources are dispersed throughout multiple platforms, lacking a centralized location for convenient access. The fragmentation poses a significant challenge for this population, making it extremely difficult to locate and access the specific services or health information they require. Excessive fragmentation not only affect access but also results in poor technical service delivery, inefficient resource utilization, and diminished user satisfaction.³⁹

Furthermore, the study shows the existence of an educational resource gap among the evaluated websites, particularly in the absence of materials tailored to the unique needs of recently released individuals. While mental health and substance use information is well-covered, there's a noticeable gap in addressing HIV and chronic health issues. Addressing this gap is essential, as it directly impacts the population's ability to navigate and make informed decisions about managing and preventing diseases. Targeted educational resources play a pivotal role in enhancing health literacy and empowerment, contributing to improved health outcomes.⁴⁰

Overall, it becomes imperative to channel efforts into establishing a centralized platform in NYS that consolidates essential resources and services for recently released individuals. Additionally, integrating tailored educational materials within this platform is crucial to communicate the knowledge and skills necessary for informed decision-making about health. Such initiatives align with broader public health goals, emphasizing accessibility, equity, and empowerment for vulnerable populations.

Conclusion

Using the findings from the focused content analysis and the literature research, this study provides an overview of the health issues that face recently released individuals. The review of the literature provides insight into the health issues that formerly incarcerated individuals struggle with, such as substance abuse, heart disease, uncontrolled hypertension, cancer, mental health disorders, and an increased risk of HIV diagnosis^{14,15,16,17}. Its complexity highlights the significance to address the variety of health needs this population has. Addressing mental health needs, providing comprehensive healthcare services, and implementing effective transitional programs are key elements in ensuring the successful reintegration of individuals into society and reducing the risk of adverse outcomes post-release.^{19,24}

The study also highlights significant barriers to accessing healthcare for recently released individuals. These barriers include a lack of knowledge about available services, extended wait times, and difficulties in obtaining chronic medications.³⁰ The discontinuity between prison-based and post-release medical care, along with challenges in scheduling appointments, further exacerbates the existing hurdles. Bridging these gaps in healthcare support is crucial for the successful reintegration and overall well-being of recently released individuals.

Overall, the period immediately following release from prison is a critical juncture that demands targeted interventions. Through a multidimensional approach, encompassing both mental and physical health, it is possible to empower this population.

The content analysis offers a critical perspective on the state of the resources that are currently available by evaluating the level of sufficiency and relevance of online health information for individuals released from incarceration. The analysis has revealed positive aspects along with possibilities for development in the way health information is delivered.

The fragmentation of resources and gaps in health education information in the websites emphasize the need for a comprehensive and centralized platform. Closing this gap can help people make better decisions, give them more self-confidence, and eventually improve the health of those who have just been released from incarceration. This study advocates for the development of online platforms that not only enhance the accessibility of health information but also align with the diverse and critical health needs of this vulnerable population.

References:

1. Binswanger IA, Stern MF, Deyo RA, Heagerty PJ, Cheadle A, Elmore JG, Koepsell TD. Release from prison—a high risk of death for former inmates. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2007 Jan 11;356(2):157-65.
2. Bui J, Wendt M, Bakos A. Understanding and addressing health disparities and health needs of justice-involved populations. *Public Health Reports*. 2019 May;134(1_suppl):3S-7S.
3. Schnittker J, Massoglia M, Uggen C. incarceration and the health of the african american community. *Du Bois Review: Social Science Research on Race*. 2011;8(1):133-41.
4. Freudenberg N, Daniels J, Crum M, Perkins T, Richie BE. Coming home from jail: the social and health consequences of community reentry for women, male adolescents, and their families and communities. *American journal of public health*. 2005 Oct;95(10):1725-36.
5. Taxman FS. Building effective service delivery mechanisms for justice-involved individuals: An under-researched area. *Health & Justice*. 2014 Dec;2:1-2.
6. White MD, Marsh EE. Content analysis: A flexible methodology. *Library trends*. 2006;55(1):22-45.
7. Levac, D., Colquhoun, H. & O'Brien, K.K. Scoping studies: advancing the methodology. *Implementation Sci* 5, 69 (2010). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1748-5908-5-69>
8. Kariminia, Azar, et al. "Extreme cause-specific mortality in a cohort of adult prisoners—1988 to 2002: a data-linkage study." *International journal of epidemiology* 36.2 (2007): 310-316.
9. Fahmy, Chantal. "First weeks out: Social support stability and health among formerly incarcerated men." *Social Science & Medicine* 282 (2021): 114141.
10. Golembeski, Cynthia, and Robert Fullilove. "Criminal (in) justice in the city and its associated health consequences." *American Journal of Public Health* 98.Supplement_1 (2008): S185-S190.
11. Pratt, Daniel, et al. "Suicide in recently released prisoners: a population-based cohort study." *The Lancet* 368.9530 (2006): 119-123.
12. Zlodre, Jakov, and Seena Fazel. "All-cause and external mortality in released prisoners: systematic review and meta-analysis." *American journal of public health* 102.12 (2012): e67-e75.
13. Jones, Daniel, and Alan Maynard. "Suicide in recently released prisoners: a systematic review." *Mental Health Practice* 17.3 (2013).
14. Binswanger, Ingrid A., et al. "Mortality after prison release: opioid overdose and other causes of death, risk factors, and time trends from 1999 to 2009." *Annals of internal medicine* 159.9 (2013): 592-600.
15. Howell, Benjamin A., et al. "Incarceration history and uncontrolled blood pressure in a multi-site cohort." *Journal of general internal medicine* 31 (2016): 1496-1502.
16. Aminawung, Jenerius A., et al. "Cancer incidence among incarcerated and formerly incarcerated individuals: A statewide retrospective cohort study." *Cancer Medicine* (2023).
17. Ojikutu BO, Srinivasan S, Bogart LM, Subramanian SV, Mayer KH. Mass incarceration and the impact of prison release on HIV diagnoses in the US South. *PLoS One*. 2018 Jun 11;13(6):e0198258. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0198258. PMID: 29889837; PMCID: PMC5995372.

18. Frank, Joseph W., et al. "Emergency department utilization among recently released prisoners: a retrospective cohort study." *BMC emergency medicine* 13 (2013): 1-8.
19. O'Connor, Allyson W., Jeanne M. Sears, and Deborah Fulton-Kehoe. "Overdose and substance-related mortality after release from prison in Washington State: 2014–2019." *Drug and alcohol dependence* 241 (2022): 109655.
20. Møller, L. F., et al. "Acute drug-related mortality of people recently released from prisons." *Public health* 124.11 (2010): 637-639.
21. Mital, Sasha, Jessica Wolff, and Jennifer J. Carroll. "The relationship between incarceration history and overdose in North America: A scoping review of the evidence." *Drug and alcohol dependence* 213 (2020): 108088.
22. Merrall, Elizabeth LC, et al. "Meta-analysis of drug-related deaths soon after release from prison." *Addiction* 105.9 (2010): 1545-1554.
23. Spittal, M. J., et al. "Modifiable risk factors for external cause mortality after release from prison: a nested case–control study." *Epidemiology and psychiatric sciences* 28.2 (2019): 224-233
24. Van Dooren, Kate, Stuart A. Kinner, and Simon Forsyth. "Risk of death for young ex-prisoners in the year following release from adult prison." *Australian and New Zealand journal of public health* 37.4 (2013): 377-382.
25. Andrews, Jessica Y., and Stuart A. Kinner. "Understanding drug-related mortality in released prisoners: a review of national coronial records." *BMC public health* 12.1 (2012): 1-7.
26. Rosen, David L., Victor J. Schoenbach, and David A. Wohl. "All-cause and cause-specific mortality among men released from state prison, 1980–2005." *American journal of public health* 98.12 (2008): 2278-2284.
27. Addison, Helena A., et al. "Mental health outcomes in formerly incarcerated Black men: A systematic mixed studies review." *Journal of Advanced Nursing* 78.7 (2022): 1851-1869.
28. Freudenberg, Nicholas, et al. "Coming home from jail: the social and health consequences of community reentry for women, male adolescents, and their families and communities." *American journal of public health* 95.10 (2005): 1725-1736.
29. Krinsky, Clarissa S., et al. "Drugs, detention, and death: a study of the mortality of recently released prisoners." *The American journal of forensic medicine and pathology* 30.1 (2009): 6-9.
30. Binswanger, Ingrid A., et al. "'From the prison door right to the sidewalk, everything went downhill,' a qualitative study of the health experiences of recently released inmates." *International journal of law and psychiatry* 34.4 (2011): 249-255.
31. Rao NR, Mohapatra M, Mishra S, Joshi A. Evaluation of dengue-related health information on the internet. Perspectives in Health Information Management/AHIMA, American Health Information Management Association. 2012;9
32. Hardman MP, Reynolds KA, Petty SK, Pryor TA, Pierce SK, Bernstein MT, Furer P. An evaluation of the quality of online perinatal depression information. BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth. 2022 Dec;22(1):1-1.
33. Zhang Y. Consumer health information searching process in real life settings. Assoc Inf Sci Technol 2012;49(1):1-10.
34. Fortune society. URL: <https://fortunesociety.org/> [Accessed 12/15/2023]

35. Legal action center. URL: <https://www.lac.org/> [Accessed: 12/15/2023]
36. Re-entry programs. URL: <https://www.reentryprograms.com/> [Accessed: 12/15/2023]
37. Probation information network. URL: <https://www.probationinfo.org/> [Accessed: 12/15/2023]
38. NYC 311: Incarcerated person jail release services. URL: <https://portal.311.nyc.gov/article/?kanumber=KA-02820> [Accessed: 12/15/2023]
39. Ramagem C, Urrutia S, Griffith T, Cruz M, Fabrega R, Holder R, Montenegro H. Combating health care fragmentation through integrated health services delivery networks. *Int J Integr Care*. 2011 Aug 1;11(Suppl):e100. PMID: PMC3184820.
40. Stormacq C, Wosinski J, Boillat E, Van den Broucke S. Effects of health literacy interventions on health-related outcomes in socioeconomically disadvantaged adults living in the community: a systematic review. *JBI evidence synthesis*. 2020 Jul 1;18(7):1389-469.